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USE OF ADDITIVES OF FUNCTIONAL PURPOSE IN THE FOOD FOR THE ATHLETES

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Abstract

The article studies biochemical composition and nutritional values of various forms of spirulina. It also studies calcium content and demonstrates the prospects of its use for the athletes. The opinion is expressed that spirulina biomass can be used in healthy food for the athletes, as physiologically active high nutritional value additive of functional purpose for production of the new food.

Keywords: athletes, food, protein, functional, calcium.

Introduction

In the recent years the great attention is paid to studying of such negative effects as: unbalanced diet, unfavorable environmental conditions, stress etc. increasing the risks of development of various diseases [1].

Consumption of the food / food products has always been necessary and natural need of the humans, though attitude to them has gradually changed, depending of changes of the social conditions [3].

The athlete's body is self-renovating and self-regulating system where the basis of metabolism is provided by the food products consumed. According to the modern nutrition theories, the selected food products not only meet the physiological requirements of the human body but they also can have so called functional purpose [2].

The main way of providing human organism with the substances necessary for life is inclusion of so-called functional food products into the diet [4, 6].

Athletes' life style follows quite tight schedules, including daily training and competitions. Extensive load requires from the athletes increased energy spending. Consequently, the athletes' diet requires additional ingredients to ensure rapid restoration in the periods of competitions, improve training length, intensity and contribute to improvement of the emotions and will.

Studies showed that including of the functional additives into the athletes' basic diet ensures increase of the training length and extensity, promotes better emotions and will in the period of competitions.

Goal of the research

Goal of the research was development of wholesome high energy food product of functional purpose for the athletes, with minimal content of other additional ingredients.

Materials and methods

To achieve the stated goal, we have selected spirulina. Humans and animals mostly consume two spirulina species: *Spirulina platensis* and *Arthrospira maxima*., with commercial name Spirulina. Name spirulina, in the opinion of different taxonomists, either is cyanobacteria genus or it is syndrome of *Arthrospira* genus.

Light and heat comprise the necessary condition for growth of spirulina algae. Its most rapid growth and propagation occurs at 32-38°C temperature.

The key advantages of spirulina, as food product include: high biological value of protein (60-65%), good absorption (40-50%) and digestion (70%).

We conducted researches on spirulina biomass¹, spirulina extract and spirulina acetone preparation. We have studied content of the key nutrients (proteins, fats, carbohydrates) and calcium in it. On the basis of test results, we have calculated the nutritional value of spirulina. We conducted research applying the following methods: we have measured protein content by Bradford method; fat content was measured by extraction method; carbohydrate content – by K.N. Chizhova and A.N. Sonkina micro-method. Calcium content was measured by spectrophotometry.

Research results

Discussion. At the first stage we have studied UV absorption spectrum of spirulina, see figure. As it can be seen on the figure, maximal absorption of the solution containing spirulina occurs at 591-592 nm wavelength.

As one of the objectives of our research was studying of spirulina nutritional value, we regarded that it would be reasonable to study content of the proteins, fats and carbohydrates in spirulina, applying the abovementioned methods. Table shows that protein content in spirulina biomass is quite high, 68.2%, indicating that spirulina could be used as wholesome additive for the food intended for the athletes; see the Table 1.

At the same time, protein has one of the decisive functions in formation of the muscle tissues in the body of the athlete.

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Table 1.
Biochemical composition and nutritional value of spirulina

Sample	Carbohydrates, %	Fats,%	Proteins, %	Nutritional value			
				Theoretical		Practical	
				Kcal	KJ	Kcal	KJ
Spirulina, green biomass	21,4 ± 0,9	6,5± 0,6	68,2 ± 0,5	411,5	1728,5	362,3	1520,7
Spirulina, acetone preparation	20,2 ± 0,2	5,8± 0,1	67,6 ± 0,1	398,35	1673,1	349,7	1468,4
Spirulina, commercial	19,7± 0,7	5,5± 0,4	67,2 ± 0,5	392,2	1647,2	344,3	1445,7

We have studied calcium content in the spirulina samples. High calcium content was found in spirulina biomass – 14.2%; in acetone preparation – 13.8%; in commercial – 13.7%. High calcium content in spirulina biomass shows that spirulina absorbs calcium in the cultivation process and accumulates its quite significant quantity. Consequently, we can state that spirulina cultivated in geo-ecological conditions of Georgia can be regarded as proper source of calcium for the athlete's organism. On the basis of our researches the following conclusions can be made:

1. Biochemical contents and nutritional values of various forms of spirulina were studied; 2. Spirulina cultivation to obtain biomass is possible in geo-ecological conditions of Georgia; 3. Due to high calcium content, spirulina could be regarded as good source of calcium for the organism; 4. The opinion was expressed that due to high nutritional value, spirulina biomass could be used for healthy diet of the athletes, in particular, as physiologically active, non-traditional, wholesome additive for the new food products with high nutritional value of functional purpose.

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